

THIOHYDANTOINS AND THEIR DERIVATIVES AND USE OF SOME OF THEM IN THE ESTIMATION OF SILVER, MERCURY AND COPPER

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o-Tolylthiohydantoin and its arylidene and *N*-methylarylidene derivatives and its condensation products with nitroso compounds, ketones and quinones have been prepared. By condensation of thiohydantoin with α -naphthaldehyde and subsequent reduction with stannous chloride and hydrolysis by $(\text{BaOH})_2$, α -naphthylalanine has been prepared. The thiohydantoin has been used successfully for estimation of Ag and Hg, and dimethylaminobenzylidene-thiohydantoin for estimation of copper.

Usefulness of thiohydantoin in medicine as insecticides, resin intermediates and corrosion inhibitors is well recognised. They provide a convenient route to the synthesis of α -amino-acids, thiazole derivatives and antispasmodics. In an earlier investigation (Pujari and Rout, this *Journal*, 1954, 31, 937) usefulness of arylidene-thiohydantoin in analytical procedures for estimation of certain metallic ions was indicated. In the present investigation, their analytical importance has been studied in detail. One of the arylidene derivatives (*o*-naphthylidene derivative) has also been used for the synthesis of an amino-acid, α -naphthylalanine. Preparation of quinolythiohydantoin is in progress.

The thiohydantoin used for the analytical investigations are *o*- and *p* tolyl derivatives. The preparation of *p*-tolylthiohydantoin was described in a previous investigation (*loc. cit.*). *o*-Tolylthiohydantoin has been prepared in the same manner by the reaction of *o*-tolylisothiocyanate and glycine. The arylidene compounds were prepared by condensing *o*-tolylthiohydantoin with aromatic aldehydes in presence of glacial acetic acid and anhydrous sodium acetate. The reaction proceeds as follows:

These have been methylated by methyl iodide. *o*-Tolylthiohydantoin has been condensed with ketones, quinones and nitroso compounds, the condensation being carried out in presence of acetic anhydride. Preparation of one compound of each class has been illustrated in the Experimental.

For the synthesis of α -naphthylalanine, the following procedure was followed. *p*-Tolylthiohydantoin was first condensed with α -naphthaldehyde and the resulting arylidene compound was desulphurised by chloroacetic acid to yield the corresponding hydantoin. The resulting hydantoin compound was reduced by stannous chloride to the corresponding reduced hydantoin. This was converted into α -naphthylalanine by prolonged boiling with a large excess of barium hydroxide.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

o-Tolylisothiocyanate was prepared by the method of Dains, Brewster and Olander ("Organic Synthesis", Vol. I, p. 437). *o*-Tolylthiohydantoin was prepared by the method given in Beilstein, XXIV, Erste p. 293.

4-Benzylidene-1-o-tolyl-2-thiohydantoin.—Benzaldehyde (0.6 g.) and *o*-tolylthiohydantoin (1 g.) were refluxed in glacial acetic acid (20 c.c.) in presence of anhydrous sodium acetate (1.5 g.) for nearly 2½ hours on a wire-gauge. After heating for half an hour, the solution became clear. The reaction mixture was further heated for 2 hours. The clear brown solution was then poured into water, when a pale yellow precipitate appeared. After allowing it to stand overnight, the precipitate was filtered off and recrystallised from alcohol, m.p. 192°, yield 92%. (Found: N, 9.23; S, 11.14. $C_{17}H_{14}O_2N_2S$ requires N, 9.52; S, 10.88%).

Condensation with other aldehydes was also effected in the above manner. Their m.p. and analytical data are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

4-Arylidene-1-o-tolyl-2-thiohydantoin.

Aldehydes taken.	M.P.	% Yield.	% S u l p h u r.	
			Found.	Calc.
<i>o</i> -Nitrobenzaldehyde	145°	65%	9.56	9.44
<i>m</i> - " "	182°	65	9.48	9.44
<i>p</i> - " "	198°	75	9.37	9.44
<i>o</i> -Hydroxy "	175°	60	10.50	10.32
<i>p</i> - " "	230°	70	10.29	10.32
Anisaldehyde	130°	85	9.82	9.88
Vanillin	186°	78	9.25	9.41
Furfuraldehyde	128°	65	11.79	11.27
Cinnamaldehyde	185°	80	10.14	10.00
<i>p</i> -Dimethylaminobenzaldehyde	116°	75	9.47	9.49

N-Methyl-4-benzylidene-1-o-tolylthiohydantoin.—To finely pulverised KOH (1 g.), dissolved in 95% alcohol (8 c.c.), the above compound (1 g.) was added, when a bright yellow potassium salt separated out. Methyl iodide (3 g.) was then added in small portions at a time and finally the reaction mixture was refluxed on a steam-bath for 3 to 4 hours until neutral to litmus. On cooling, the methylated thiohydantoin separated out and the inorganic salt formed was dissolved out by stirring with water. The thiohydantoin was filtered and recrystallised from alcohol, m.p. 52°, yield 85%. (Found: S, 10.12. $C_{16}H_{16}ON_2S$ requires S, 10.39%). Other arylidene derivatives were methylated in the same manner. Their m.p. and analytical data are described in Table II.

TABLE II

N-Methyl-4-arylidene-1-o-tolyl-2-thiohydantoin.

M.P.	132°	140°	154°	130°	172°	185°	167°	85°	92° (decomp.)	144°
% Yield	65	65	90	80	70	60	70	60	70	80
% Sulphur (found)	9.36	9.28	9.25	10.21	10.16	9.75	9.32	10.56	9.85	5.32
% Sulphur (calc.)	9.09	9.09	9.09	9.87	9.87	9.47	9.04	10.73	9.58	9.12

* The aldehydes taken correspond to those shown in Table I in the same order.

Condensation of o-Tolylthiohydantoin with α -Nitroso- β -naphthol.—A mixture of *o*-tolylthiohydantoin (1 g.) and α -nitroso- β -naphthol (0.8 g.) was heated under reflux in presence of acetic anhydride (15 c.c.) on a sand-bath for 1 hour. The original dark green solution finally assumed a deep brown shade. The mixture was allowed to cool and then poured into water when a brown gummy product separated out. On keeping for 24 hours, the gum hardened up and became crystalline. This was filtered off, washed with hot water, dissolved in warm dilute NaOH solution (20%) and reprecipitated on acidification with HCl (dil.) making the solution just acidic. Finally it was recrystallised from alcohol, m. p. 230°, yield 35%. (Found: S, 9.04. $C_{20}H_{18}O_2N_2S$ requires S, 8.86%).

Reaction with *p*-nitrosodimethylaniline was brought about also in the above manner, yield 36%, m.p. 174° (decomp.). (Found: S, 9.63. $C_{18}H_{18}ON_2S$ requires S, 9.47%).

Condensation with Isatin.—A mixture of *o*-tolylthiohydantoin (1.45 g.) and isatin (1 g.) was heated under reflux in presence of acetic anhydride (15 c.c.) for about 1 hour. The reaction, which was very vigorous at first, gradually subsided and it was complete when the mixture assumed a brownish yellow shade. The reaction mixture was cooled and poured into water when a precipitate came down. This was filtered, washed with hot water and finally crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 228° (decomp.), yield 82%. (Found: S, 9.44. $C_{18}H_{12}ON_2S$ requires S, 9.55%).

Condensation with anthraquinone, benzil, Michler's ketone, quinone and alizarin was effected also in the above manner. Their m.p. and analytical data are reported in Table III.

TABLE III

Condensation of o-tolylthiohydantoin with ketones or quinones.

Nature of ketones or quinones condensed.	M.P.	% Yield.	% S u l p h u r.	
			Found.	Calc.
Anthraquinone	112°	60	8.16	8.08
Quinone	85°	65	9.89	9.64
Michler's ketone	135°	70	7.38	7.01
Alizarin	96°	62	6.81	6.90

α-Naphthylalanine

To accomplish its synthesis, the following intermediate compounds were prepared.

(a). *4-α-Naphthylidene-1-p-tolylthiohydantoin*.—A mixture of *p*-tolylthiohydantoin (4 g.), 1-naphthaldehyde (3 g.), glacial acetic acid (15 to 20 c.c.) and fused sodium acetate (4 to 5 g.) was heated in an oil-bath at 140°. A clear solution was obtained at first. After 1 hour's heating, the condensation product began to separate from the hot solution. The heating was continued for 3 to 4 hours. The reaction mixture was mixed with water, cooled and filtered. The compound was purified by recrystallisation from alcohol, m.p. 156°, yield 70%. (Found: S, 9.12. $C_{21}H_{18}ON_2S$ requires S, 9.3%).

(b). *4-α-Naphthylidene-1-p-tolylhydantoin*.—The corresponding thiohydantoin (5 g.), prepared as above, was digested with chloroacetic acid (13 g.) in about 30 c.c. of water for 6 hours in an oil-bath at 130-40°. On concentrating to half of its bulk and cooling and filtering, the product was isolated, m.p. 180°, yield 80%. (Found: N, 8.25. $C_{21}H_{18}O_2N_2$ requires N, 8.54%).

(c). *Hydantoin of α-Naphthylalanine*.—For reduction of the preceding hydantoin, the following reaction mixture was prepared: 5 g. of hydantoin, 12.5 g. of $SuCl_2 \cdot 2H_2O$, 50 c.c. of alcohol and 75 c.c. of 20% HCl. The mixture was heated on a boiling water-bath for about 2 hours and the excess of alcohol was evaporated off. The residue left behind was triturated with water, filtered and the insoluble precipitate was treated as described below. The aqueous filtrate was saturated with H_2S to precipitate tin as sulphide. After filtering off this sulphide precipitate and evaporating the filtrate to dryness, no organic residue was left.

The insoluble precipitate was proved to be the desired reduction product, m.p. 180°, yield 75%. (Found: N, 8.31. $C_{21}H_{18}O_2N_2$ requires N, 8.43 %).

(d). *Hydrolysis of the Reduced Hydantoin to α-Naphthylalanine*.—This was found to be very resistant to hydrolysis. The pure reduced hydantoin (3 g.) was suspended in about 500 c.c. of hot saturated solution of barium hydroxide and the mixture boiled under reflux till the evolution of NH_3 had ceased. This actually required digestion over a period of 40 to 50 hours. The barium was then precipitated as barium sulphate by adding the requisite amount of sulphuric acid and bringing the solution to an exact neutral point to litmus. After filtering off barium sulphate, the clear aqueous solution was evaporated to dryness when the amino-acid was obtained, m.p. 235-40°, yield 70%. (Found: N, 6.25. $C_{13}H_{13}O_2N$ requires N, 6.51%).

Use of p-Tolylthiohydantoin in the Estimation of Silver and Mercury

Estimation of Mercury.—A standard solution of mercuric chloride was prepared by weight standard and was further standardised by zinc ammonium thiocyanate method.

$HgCl_2$ solution (10 c.c., containing 0.04558 g. of Hg) was taken in a beaker and about 30 c.c. of water was added to it. The reagent (0.2 g.), dissolved in

about 20 c.c. of alcohol, was added gradually with stirring. The complex formed was warmed slightly on a water-bath, kept overnight and then filtered hot on G₃ crucible. The precipitate was first washed with hot water and then with water-alcohol mixture. It was dried at 105° and finally weighed. Since the weights of the complex obtained in the different experiments varied (of course within a small margin), it was considered desirable to estimate the total content of Hg in the complex which would serve as a further check on the results. For this, the procedure was slightly modified. The precipitate was collected on Whatman No. 42 filter paper and dried. The precipitate was then transferred as much as possible from the dried filter paper into an iron crucible. The filter paper was carefully made into small pieces which were put into the iron crucible along with adhering particles and the Hg content in the total quantity of the complex placed in the iron crucible was estimated by Gold crucible method. The results so obtained were then compared with the weight of mercury taken in the form of HgCl₂. The results agreed within 0.5%. Theoretically the weight of the complex on the basis of the proposed structure should be 0.1391 g. The weights of the complex and the weights of mercury obtained in the different experiments are recorded in Table IV. The weight of mercury obtained in each of these experiments points to the following structural formula for the complex.

TABLE IV

Hg taken = 0.04558 g,

Wt. of the complex (g.) ...	0.1474	0.1482	0.1478	0.1486
Hg found (g.) ...	0.04533	0.04522	0.04611	0.04588
Error (g.) ...	-0.00025	-0.00036	-0.00053	+0.0003

Estimation of Silver.—A standard solution of silver nitrate was prepared by weight standard and also estimated by Mohr's method of titration using potassium chromate as indicator.

The salt solution (10 c.c. containing 0.0266 g. of AgNO₃) was taken in a beaker. The *p_H* of the solution was maintained at 3.0 by adding 50 c.c. of acetate buffer. An excess of the reagent solution (0.1 %) was added to the mixture dropwise with constant stirring till complete precipitation. The complex formed was slightly warmed on a water-bath, kept overnight and then filtered hot. The precipitate was first washed with hot water, then with 25% warm alcohol and finally with ether to free it from the reagent. The complex was dried at 120° and weighed.

Theoretically the yield of the complex on the basis of the proposed formula by taking 0.0169 g. of silver should be 0.04898 and by taking 0.04223 g. of silver, 0.1225 g. The results, which are shown in Table V, show excellent agreement with the values calculated on the basis of the proposed structure.

TABLE V

Ag. taken (g.)	...	0.0169	0.0169	0.0169	0.04223	0.04223	0.04223
Wt. of the complex (g.)	...	0.04889	0.04892	0.04882	0.1221	0.1216	0.1228
Ag found (g.)	...	0.01687	0.01688	0.01685	0.04212	0.04194	0.04236
Error (g.)	...	-0.00003	-0.00002	-0.00005	+0.00012	+0.00029	+0.00013

Ag found was calculated from the percentage of silver in the silver complex which was analysed to the formula $C_{10}H_9ON_2SAg$. (Found: N, 8.75; S, 9.95; Ag, 34.45. $C_{10}H_9ON_2SAg$ requires N, 8.94; S, 10.23; Ag, 34.5%).

The amount of silver present in the complex was determined as follows. A definite amount of the complex was weighed in a tared porcelain crucible and heated continuously over a small flame. When the contents of the crucible became greyish white, the crucible was heated to red heat for 15 to 20 minutes. It was then cooled in a desiccator and the contents weighed. The process of ignition, cooling and weighing was repeated until a constant weight was obtained.

TABLE VI

Complex taken (g.)	...	0.1250	0.1180	0.1456	0.2505	0.2674	0.2728
Silver found (g.)	...	0.04342	0.04172	0.05044	0.08632	0.09238	0.09409

Use of p-Dimethylaminobenzylidene-p-tolylthiohydantoin in the Estimation of Copper

A standard solution of $CuSO_4 \cdot 5H_2O$ was prepared by weight standard and was further standardised by iodometric method using starch as indicator.

Copper sulphate solution (5 c.c. containing 0.01592 g. of Cu) was taken in a beaker and about 10 c.c. of dilute ammonia and 10 c.c. of water were added to it. The solution of the reagent (0.3 g.) in 25 c.c. of rectified spirit, and 15 c.c. of acetone were then added to it with constant stirring. After stirring for 10 to 15 minutes, 5 c.c. of ammonia, 10 c.c. of water and 5 c.c. of acetone were again added, and the whole warmed for 5 minutes on a hot water-bath and then allowed to stand overnight. The complex was filtered through a previously weighed G_2 crucible and then washed with hot water. The product being somewhat soluble in warm alcohol presented some difficulties. An 1:1 cold mixture of rectified spirit and water was found by trial to be most suitable for washing. It was then dried at about 105° and weighed.

As variation in the weights of the complex, of course within a small range, was observed, it was considered necessary to estimate the content of copper in the weight of the complex obtained in each experiment. This was done as follows. The precipitate was collected on Whatman No. 42 filter paper and dried. The precipitate was transferred as much as possible from the dried filter paper into a

porcelain crucible. The filter paper was then carefully ignited into ash and was then put into the crucible along with the adhering particles. The weight of copper found in each experiment points to the proposed structure for the complex (same as in Hg complex, $\frac{1}{2}$ Cu for $\frac{1}{2}$ Hg). The weights of the complex and the weight of copper obtained in different experiments are recorded in Table VII.

TABLE VII

Cu taken = 0.01586 g.

Wt. of the complex (g.) ...	0.1898	0.1914	0.1926	0.1922
Cu found (g.) ...	0.01589	0.01612	0.01609	0.01597
Error (g.) ...	0.0003	0.0026	0.0003	0.00011

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